

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CARRYING OUT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH WORK IN MUSEUMS

Novruzova N.

Nakhchivan State University

Abstract

Scientific research work in museums is one of the most important issues. Special attention should always be paid to this area. It is important to carry out scientific-research works in museums, carry out separate researches for each of the exhibits and make innovations. First of all, let's take a look at what methods are used to determine historicity.

Keywords: scientific research work, museum, expertise, method, research.

In general, one of the topical issues in the field of museology today is the rules for conducting scientific research and expertise. Because students who graduate from this specialty should know that museums are not only an institution where exhibits are exhibited, but also a scientific-research center. Museum workers of the future must learn not only how to enter and display exhibits in the museum, but also how to determine its historicity, how to distinguish between original works and fake works, and how to conduct expertise.

It is important to carry out scientific-research works in museums, carry out separate researches for each of the exhibits and make innovations. First of all, let's take a look at what methods are used to determine historicity. (Gurbanova, Alizade, 2011). In general, one of the topical issues in the field of museology today is the rules for conducting scientific research and conducting expertise. Because students who graduate from this specialty should know that museums are not only an institution where exhibits are displayed, but also a scientific-research center. Museum workers of the future must learn not only how to enter and display exhibits in the museum, but also to determine its historicity, to distinguish between original and fake works, and to conduct expertise.

The following methods are used to determine the historicity.

Descriptive method-historical genetic method

With this method, the properties, changes and successive detection of the studied object are carried out in the historical process. According to the form of expression of the information, it is descriptive in nature. The historical-genetic method is the most flexible and the most accessible, universal method. This method makes it possible to show cause-and-effect relationships, regularities of historical development, and to characterize events and personalities. This method reveals the individual characteristics of the researcher.

Historical development method - critical method - we know to a high degree that it is one of the great factors influencing development in every field of science. Open this method of cleaning. We create any object with another object that explores it, and several of their objects may appear. At this time, we can draw conclusions about the presence of other characteristics based on those studies. But care and attention that the known properties of a certain object should be wider than that of the object being studied.

References

1. Elfira Gurbanova, Apdin Alizade "Organization and methodology of scientific research work in museums" Baku, Teknur, 2011.